

Supplementary Material - MAGE: Strain Level Profiling of Metagenome Samples

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1 Results on Real Dataset

Table 1 shows the comparison of benchmarked tools on the real dataset which consisted of four E.Coli strains. The column 1 of the table 1 depicts the name of the four E.Coli strains in the sample while column 2 shows the ground truth abundances of the four E.Coli strains. We note that GOTTCHA1 uses a specialized reference database of only bacterial genomes. Last row of the table shows the number of strains identified by each tool.

Strain Name	Truth	MetaPhlan strainer	Centrifuge 1	Centrifuge 2	GOTTCHA 1	GOTTCHA 2	Kraken2 V1	Kraken2 V2	MAGE
SEC470	0.80	0	0.0000	0	0	0	0	0	0.3303
UT189	0.15	0	0.0000	0	0	0	8.46E-05	0.0021	0
Sakai	0.049	0	0.0049	8.17E-08	0.3049	0.1356	0	0	0
24377A	0.001	0	0.0149	4.71E-06	0.0289	0.0128	0	0	0
No. of Predicted Strains	4	1	130	185	8	36	916	125	4

Table 1. Strain internal ID and corresponding Strain Name for HC-1 dataset

2 Benchmarking tools

In order to benchmark MAGE with the other tools we map the output strains from all tools to their corresponding RefSeq IDs. All the performance metrics are then calculated based on these RefSeq IDs. For all the datasets that are used for benchmarking with other tools, the RefSeq IDs of the constituent ground truth strains are known. Below are the details of output formats of each tool used for benchmarking along with the details on how we tracked the strains in each case. All strains that map to the ground truth RefSeq IDs are considered as TP and the remaining strains are considered as FP.

- MetaPhlan_strainer : MetaPhlan_strainer reports the GCF ids for tracked strains along with their abundance. We mapped the GCF to the RefSeq IDs using NCBI. Sample output of MetaPhlan_strainer is provided in Fig 1.

k_Bacteria p_Firmicutes c_Bacillio Lactobacillales f_Enterococcaceae g_Enterococcus s_Enterococcus faecium t_Enterococcus faecium unclassified	9.98147
f_Enterobacteriaceae g_Klebsiella s_Klebsiella pneumoniae t_Klebsiella pneumoniae unclassified	7.33697
k_Bacteria p_Firmicutes c_Bacillio Lactobacillales f_Lactobacillaceae g_Lactobacillus s_Lactobacillus delbrueckii t_Lactobacillus delbrueckii unclassified	6.24379
k_Bacteria p_Firmicutes c_Bacillio Bacillales f_Bacillaceae g_Bacillus s_Bacillus cereus thuringiensis t_Bacillus cereus thuringiensis unclassified	5.77688
k_Bacteria p_Actinobacteria c_Actinobacteria o_Actinomycetales f_Mycobacteriaceae g_Mycobacterium s_Mycobacterium tuberculosis bovis africanum canettii t_Mycobacterium tuberculosis bovis africanum canettii unclassified	3.33059
k_Bacteria p_Proteobacteria c_Alphaproteobacteria o_Rhizobiales f_Bradyrhizobiaceae g_Rhodopseudomonas s_Rhodopseudomonas palustris t_GCF_000013745	3.31266

Fig. 1. Sample output from MetaPhlan_strainer

69.34	14754013	7033646	93907374	2921807 F	543	Enterobacteriaceae
26.97	5739758	514410	19984426	1348805 G	561	Escherichia
24.24	5158529	5076854	16618784	1135428 S	562	Escherichia coli
0.08	17801	17801	50359	4576 S1	745156	Escherichia coli 1303
0.08	16747	0	49694	4571 S1	2233553	Escherichia coli O43
0.08	16747	16747	49694	4571 S2	1055541	Escherichia coli O43 str. RM10042
0.03	6997	0	13626	1277 S1	1072458	Escherichia coli O7:K1
0.03	6997	6997	13626	1277 S2	1072459	Escherichia coli O7:K1 str. CE10
0.03	6919	6919	16896	1611 S1	199310	Escherichia coli CFT073

Fig. 2. Sample output from Kraken2

- Kraken2 : For Kraken2 we use the strain names to map the the strains to RefSeq IDs using NCBI. Sample output of Kraken2 is provided in Figure 2.
- GOTTCHA : For mapping strain IDs from GOTTCHA profiling output we again use the strain names to map to the corresponding RefSeq IDs using NCBI. Sample output of GOTTCHA is provided in Figure 3.

strain	Salmonella enterica subsp. enterica serovar Choleraesuis str. SC-867	0.05	8447	58932	1545	1545	873	6.9766781105718	0.014039490458353	6.80193905817174
strain	Lactobacillus delbrueckii subsp. bulgaricus 2038	0.0484	56513	391218	10226	0	5832	6.92261957425275	0.013930705977723	6.595377916617
strain	Escherichia coli ETEC H10407	0.0484	109226	806280	21077	19	12373	7.38175892186842	0.01485465321847	6.58537182995059
strain	Klebsiella pneumoniae subsp. pneumoniae NTUH-K2044	0.0447	20969	138237	3640	0	2205	6.59244599170204	0.0132666282481552	6.08383945075258
strain	Rhodopseudomonas palustris BisB18	0.0428	3302944	2.1E+07	547455	0	349221	6.29400952604707	0.012665725046397	5.82453162119068
strain	Escherichia coli O7:K1 str. CE10	0.0423	9850	63640	1693	0	1143	6.4609137058376	0.01300159400852	5.76136157885207
strain	Klebsiella pneumoniae KCTC 2242	0.0381	92589	627569	16488	0	9848	6.77800818671764	0.013839897826945	5.19033834904112
strain	Escherichia coli Kuzhou21	0.038	145	828	22	0	18	5.71034482758621	0.011481189710948	5.175
strain	Escherichia coli J11886	0.0319	15624	115729	3042	0	1766	7.4071300563236	0.014905706720022	4.34711892419803
strain	Escherichia coli O103:H2 str. 12009	0.0187	24855	220467	5819	0	3757	8.87012673506337	0.017849764269899	2.55131751009686
strain	Escherichia coli SMS-3-5	0.0185	57125	402407	10550	0	6377	7.0443238512035	0.014175617095571	2.51342573218491
strain	Escherichia coli UT189	0.0169	2375	13135	347	0	229	5.53052631578947	0.011129326439446	2.30640913081851
strain	Escherichia coli SE15	0.0157	6715	47780	1228	0	733	7.11541325390916	0.014318078572473	2.13427435565283
strain	Escherichia coli IHE3034	0.015	7290	43715	1140	0	722	5.99657064471879	0.012067175096096	2.04802061372887
strain	Escherichia coli APEC O78	0.0134	10472	73074	1940	0	1272	6.97803666921314	0.01404224348433	1.81929990539262
strain	Klebsiella pneumoniae CG43	0.013	25694	168183	4483	0	2940	6.54561376196777	0.013172039830239	1.76651681616705
strain	Enterococcus faecium Aus0085	0.0126	74429	468175	12278	1068	7512	6.29022289698908	0.012658105038467	1.71158507383021
strain	Escherichia coli IA139	0.011	1940	13009	343	0	206	6.70412371134021	0.013491016996664	1.49890515155007
strain	Escherichia coli O26:H11 str. 11368	0.0102	9726	81874	2149	0	1425	6.41805469874563	0.016940038905026	1.38335726957844
strain	Salmonella enterica subsp. enterica serovar Heidelberg str. SL476	0.0095	6326	44354	1168	0	713	7.01138159974708	0.014109325886823	1.288910840505405
strain	Salmonella enterica subsp. enterica serovar Typhi str. CT18	0.0094	1371	9582	247	0	148	6.9890590809628	0.014064405254896	1.28548430372954
strain	Salmonella enterica subsp. enterica serovar Newport str. USMARC-S3124.1	0.0087	3267	20371	543	0	387	6.23538414447505	0.01254775049287	1.18442932728647
strain	Escherichia coli UMN026	0.0083	16675	109120	2905	0	2128	6.54392803598201	0.013168647566254	1.12468177648599
strain	Escherichia coli APEC O1	0.0079	7644	50894	1335	38	816	6.65803244374673	0.01339626511757	1.08039144925383

Fig. 3. Sample output from GOTTCHA

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- Centrifuge : For Centrifuge also we use the strain names to identify the corresponding RefSeq IDs using NCBI. Sample output of Centrifuge is provided in Figure 4.

Bacillus thuringiensis YBT-1518	529122	leaf	6691625	14520	669	9.27413E-07
Bacillus bombysepticus str. Wang	1330043	leaf	5295783	156667	480	8.96466E-07
Escherichia phage Rac-SA53	1759531	species	52291	3241	23	8.55854E-07
Bacillus sp. ABP14	1892404	species	5152566	33444	469	8.3433E-07
Shigella sp. MO17	1072658	species	54291	906	29	8.17924E-07
Escherichia phage JLK-2012	1147722	species	57198	5301	54	7.9063E-07
Escherichia coli O182:H21	2048779	leaf	5239738	3947	1572	7.88092E-07
Klebsiella pneumoniae subsp. rhinoscleromatis SB3432	861365	leaf	5384455	3781	1974	7.83734E-07
Aeromonas enteropelogenes	29489	species	167693	31	6	7.83489E-07
Escherichia coli O42	216592	leaf	5441997	10471	2469	7.76419E-07
Enterococcus faecium T110	1344042	leaf	2737963	8071	5783	7.72752E-07
Escherichia coli O157:H39	930407	leaf	59016	83	19	7.42741E-07
Bacillus sp. B25(2016b)	1868655	species	5113413	114291	493	7.42194E-07
Escherichia fergusonii ATCC 35469	585054	leaf	4676635	105530	8414	7.36044E-07
Escherichia coli SMS-3-5	439855	leaf	5216408	29732	2764	7.03073E-07
Escherichia coli O157:H16	930406	leaf	5162592	6770	2617	6.69214E-07
Stx2-converting phage 86	379329	species	60238	731	0	6.48606E-07
Bacillus thuringiensis serovar coreanensis	180843	leaf	6290568	10196	947	6.44783E-07
Escherichia coli O157:H43	626531	leaf	68981	32	7	6.34951E-07
Aeromonas sp. ASNIH5	1758179	species	4783196	143734	21876	6.3352E-07
Escherichia coli O157:H11	664077	leaf	5101147	5201	1520	6.24201E-07

Fig. 4. Sample output from Centrifuge

3 Comparison of Estimated Abundances

In order to compute the performance metrics for the different benchmarking tools at the level of strains, we use JSD, TVD and HD distances, as discussed in the main manuscript. For example, to compute JSD for a specific tool, we consider its abundance predictions as probabilities (given as columns in the following table) and compare it with the ground truth probability distribution. For all, predicted FP strains with non-zero abundance, the corresponding ground truth abundance is assumed to be zero.

We have also provided the raw output files for each of the tools for HC1 dataset as a separate file in the supplementary materials.

For comparison of abundance estimates of the tools, Table 2 shows the strain level abundances of the 34 ground truth strains present in HC1 dataset. The last row shows the total predictions made by each tool respectively. The strains IDs shown in the table are the internal numbering that we use. For example, strain 562_97 indicates that it is a strain from the species with NCBI tax ID 562 and 97 indicates the strain index within that taxa. Mapping of these internal IDs to the corresponding strain name is provided in Table 3.

Strain	Truth	MetaPhlan strainer	Centrifuge 1	Centrifuge 2	GOTTCHA 1	GOTTCHA 2	Kraken 1	Kraken 2	MAGE
562_1	0.02857	0.00000	0.00123	0.00001	0.07050	0.02200	0.00493	0.00496	0.02900
562_830	0.02857	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.02870
562_564	0.02857	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.02823
562_64	0.02857	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.02734
562_97	0.02857	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.02995
562_234	0.02857	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.03021
562_301	0.02857	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.02912
562_323	0.02857	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.02850
562_677	0.02857	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.02910
562_554	0.02857	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.04244
562_434	0.02857	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.02925
562_41	0.02857	0.00000	0.01497	0.00011	0.04230	0.01290	0.00490	0.00456	0.02879
562_89	0.02857	0.00000	0.00375	0.00002	0.00000	0.00000	0.01340	0.01296	0.03077
562_520	0.02857	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.02749
562_764	0.02857	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000
562_77	0.02857	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.02913
562_661	0.02857	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.02804
562_108	0.02857	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.02865
562_221	0.02857	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.02952
562_2	0.02857	0.00000	0.00007	0.00000	0.09510	0.02970	0.00000	0.00000	0.02942
1352_44	0.02857	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.02957
1352_2	0.05714	0.00000	0.00693	0.00006	0.08430	0.02630	0.06233	0.05883	0.05963
1584_3	0.02857	0.00000	0.03903	0.00023	0.04840	0.01510	0.03904	0.03703	0.02994
1584_1	0.02857	0.00000	0.03874	0.00022	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.02973
1773_58	0.02857	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.02324
1428_23	0.02857	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.03044
1076_2	0.02857	0.03313	0.04024	0.00046	0.04280	0.01330	0.47364	0.47299	0.03030
648_1	0.02857	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.02999
11786_0	0.02857	0.00000	0.03656	0.00000	0.00000	0.01560	0.34237	0.33943	0.00000
573_0	0.02857	0.00000	0.00071	0.00000	0.04470	0.01390	0.00000	0.00000	0.02802
573_101	0.02857	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.02616
573_249	0.02857	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000
1396_21	0.02857	0.00000	0.00657	0.00007	0.00000	0.00000	0.02015	0.01876	0.02858
1396_51	0.02857	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	0.02845
Total Strains Predicted.		9	341	430	84	132	785	799	34

Table 2. Strain level Abundance values for HC1 dataset

Strain ID	Strain Name
562_1	Escherichia coli CFT073
562_830	Escherichia coli NCTC86
562_564	Escherichia coli O43 str. RM10042
562_64	Escherichia coli ST540
562_97	Escherichia coli CI5
562_234	Escherichia coli C5
562_301	Escherichia coli AR_0104
562_323	Escherichia coli WCHEC000837
562_677	Escherichia coli NissleGFP_pZE21
562_554	Escherichia coli ME8067
562_434	Escherichia coli SMN013SH2
562_41	Escherichia coli O7:K1 str. CE10
562_89	Escherichia coli 1303
562_520	Escherichia coli 86-3153
562_764	Escherichia coli EK2009
562_77	Escherichia coli ECONIH1
562_661	Escherichia coli L65 chromosome
562_108	Escherichia coli SEC470
562_221	Escherichia coli MRSN346647
562_2	Escherichia coli O157:H7 str. Sakai
1352_44	Enterococcus faecium AUSMDU00004142
1352_2	Enterococcus faecium NRRL B-2354
1584_3	Lactobacillus delbrueckii subsp. bulgaricus 2038
1584_1	Lactobacillus delbrueckii subsp. bulgaricus ATCC 11842
1773_58	Mycobacterium tuberculosis I0004000-1
1428_23	Bacillus thuringiensis HS18-1
1076_2	Rhodopseudomonas palustris BisB18
648_1	Aeromonas caviae 8LM
11786_0	Moloney murine leukemia virus
573_0	Klebsiella pneumoniae subsp. pneumoniae NTUH-K2044 DNA
573_101	Klebsiella pneumoniae strain Kp_Goe_149832
573_249	Klebsiella pneumoniae subsp. pneumoniae strain KC-Pl-HB1
1396_21	Bacillus cereus 03BB108
1396_51	Bacillus cereus strain FORC_086

Table 3. Strain internal ID and corresponding Strain Name for HC-1 dataset

4 MAGE Flowchart

Fig. 5. MAGE Flowchart

5 ANI analysis of the datasets

Average Nucleotide Identity (ANI) is a similarity index between a pair of genomic sequences. Higher ANI values denote high nucleotide level similarity between two genomic sequence. In order to demonstrate the complexity of three synthetic datasets namely HC1, HC2 and LC we report the strain pair ANI values.

Fig. 6. ANI cluster map for HC1 dataset

Fig. 7. ANI cluster map for HC2 dataset

Fig. 8. ANI cluster map for LC dataset

6 ANI analysis on Strain Exclusion experiments

MAGE's performance on profiling the non-excluded TP strains is given in the main manuscript. Here we investigate ANI of the remaining strains detected by MAGE with the excluded TP strains. Figure 9 and Figure 10 shows a comparison of ANI values between the strain pairs for HC2 and LC datasets respectively. The objective of this exercise was to assess similarity of the identified strains (other than the TP strains) and the strains that were excluded from the MAGE's reference. In these two plots, the extra strains detected by MAGE are denoted with the suffix **_FP**. The remaining strains shown in the plot (without the suffix) are the strains that are present in the sample but excluded from MAGE reference.

Fig. 9. ANI cluster map for strain exclusion experiments for HC2 dataset.

Fig. 10. ANI cluster map for strain exclusion experiments for LC dataset.